

Table 3. Mean squares and *F* test for additional sum of squares corresponding to N sources.

Source of additional sum of squares	Parameter	Mean square ^a
USG	δ2η2	0.785
UIU	δ3η3	0.015
NCU	δ4η4	0.010
PCU	δ5η5	1.175**
RPCU	δ6η6	0.005
Error	σ2	0.27
	(df)	12

^a** = significant at the 0.01 level.

including parameters δ_{η_i} = 2 to 6, in FTM is given in Table 3.

The significant regression coefficients d₅ h₅ indicate that the response curves of PCU and urea are different. The values d₅ > b₁ and h₅ = c₁ indicate that the response of rice to the N in PCU was larger than to that in PU. The effect of PCU was greater than that of all other sources tried.

Carryover effects of N on the succeeding northeast monsoon crop depended on the source of N. PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha had the most carryover effect. The least carryover effects were with RPCU, NCU, UIU, and PU.

Total grain yield for both seasons was highest with PCU at 112.5 kg N/ha in the first crop and PU at 45 kg N/ha in the second crop. ■

Effect of N source on irrigated rice yield in Cameroon

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Irrigated rice has been grown in Ndop Plain, Western Cameroon, since the early 1970s without any specific fertilizer recommendation. To fertilize their rice crops, most farmers use a 20-10-10 complex recommended for coffee.

We compared the effect on rice yield of three locally available N-fertilizer products (urea, diammonium phosphate (DAP), 20-10-10 complex) applied as basal, followed by urea or ammonium sulfate (AS) topdressed during 1987-89 wet seasons (mid-Jul to mid-Dec).

Experimental soil was Tropaquept, clay loam texture, pH 5.1, 3.08% organic C, 0.23% total N, 4.5 ppm available P (Bray 1), 39% base saturation, CEC 16.6 meq/100 g, 4.12 meq/100 g Ca, 1.63 meq/100 g Mg, and 0.67 meq/100 g K (NH₄OAc extractable). N (80 kg/ha) was

applied in three equal splits: basal, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and at panicle initiation. A common 26 kg P, 33 kg K/ha were applied as triple super-phosphate and muriate of potash. P and K rates were adjusted for the amount of P and K applied with DAP and 20-10-10. Basal fertilizers were broadcast and incorporated before transplanting rice. Fertilizer was topdressed by broadcasting in plots with 5-6 cm standing water, followed by hand stirring into the soil.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Four-wk-old seedlings of IR7167-33-2-3 were transplanted in 20-m² plots at 25 × 15-cm spacing 2 d after basal fertilizer application. The plots were continuously flooded from transplanting to the late dough stage. A 12.56-m² area in the middle of each plot, leaving two border rows on all sides, was harvested for yield measurements.

N treatments did not differ significantly in two of the three years (see table).

DAP applied basal followed by urea or ammonium sulfate topdressing gave the highest yields. ■

Effect of neem extract-coated urea on rice yield and nitrogen use efficiency of transplanted rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU) and neem extract-coated urea (NECU) at 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha during 1988-89 wet seasons. Urea was coated with neem extract in 100:1 ratio on weight basis.

Experimental soil was a deep black Vertisol, with pH 7.7, 0.6% organic C, 25.1 kg available Olsen's P/ha, 240.7 kg available K/ha, and 0.2 ppm available Zn.

Half the PU was incorporated before transplanting and half in equal topdressings at tillering and panicle initiation. NECU was applied half before transplanting and half at tillering. All plots received 26.4 kg P, 33.2 kg K/ha. Rice variety Jaya was transplanted at 20 × 10-cm spacing, 3 seedlings/hill.

Grain yield was significantly higher with 150 kg N/ha applied as NECU in

Grain yield of irrigated rice as affected by nitrogen source. Ndop Plain, Cameroon. 1987-89 wet seasons.^a

Treatment ^b			N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
Basal	Topdress 1	Topdress 2		1987	1988	1989	Mean
None	None	None	0	2.5	4.6	5.1	4.1
Urea	Urea	Urea	80	3.4	6.0	6.7	5.4
20-10-10	AS	Urea	80	3.5	5.5	6.3	5.1
20-10-10	Urea	Urea	80	3.9	5.5	5.4	4.9
DAP	AS	Urea	80	4.3	5.8	6.9	5.7
DAP	Urea	Urea	80	4.3	6.2	6.9	5.8
LSD (0.05)				1.0	0.8	0.8	
CV (%)				18.1	10.0	8.4	

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bAS = ammonium sulfate.

Influence of NECU and PU on grain yield and number of productive tillers. Kota India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Mean productive tillers (no./m ²)
	1988	1989	
Control (no N)	3.6	3.5	214.0
90 kg N/ha, PU	5.0	5.0	284.0
120 kg N/ha, PU	5.7	5.6	294.6
150 kg N/ha, PU	6.0	5.9	318.6
90 kg N/ha, NECU	5.7	5.7	292.1
120 kg N/ha, NECU	6.0	5.9	306.0
150 kg N/ha, NECU	6.3	6.3	335.9
LSD (0.05)			
	0.4	0.3	20.1

both seasons, except with 150 kg N/ha as PU and 120 kg N/ha as NECU in 1988 (see table). NECU at 90 and 120 kg N/ha gave yields similar to those of PU at 120 and 150 kg N/ha.

The superiority of NECU to PU is also shown by the quadratic response functions:

$$\text{for PU, } Y = 3543 + 18N - 0.011N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99;$$

$$\text{for NECU, } Y = 3556 + 31N - 0.056N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99,$$

where Y is yield in kg/ha.

The correlation ($r = 0.98^{**}$) between productive tillers and average grain yield was significant and positive. ■

Integrated pest management – diseases

Outbreak of leaf and neck blast in boro rice crop in Bangladesh

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Epidemics of blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* have been recurring in Bangladesh every 3 or 4 yr. In the 1990 dry season (boro) crop, leaf (LBI) and neck blast (NBI) on both local and modem cultivars were higher in some locations than they had been the previous 2 yr. NBI incidence during rice crop maturity (Mar-Apr 1990) was so severe, we surveyed outbreaks in different regions.

Disease incidence (%) was assessed in 25-35 fields/region by counting the number of infected and healthy tillers or panicles of 3 × 3 hills in 9 sampling spots taken in a diagonal direction per field. Severity was rated on a 0-9 scale. The cultivars grown and prevailing tempera-

ture, humidity, and rainfall also were recorded.

The outbreak covered an average 45% of the area planted to boro rice, although its intensity varied across locations. Incidence and severity were higher in the northeastern part of the country than in the northern and southwestern parts. Disease occurred on crops growing on all types of land and soil types (see table). In region I, plots with severe NBI were also affected by low temperature.

During Jan-Mar 1990, humidity was higher at 0600 h and 1200 h, and the difference between maximum and minimum temperature was less than in 1989 (see figure). The high humidity was unusual, and frequent but light rainfall during the period kept rice leaves wet for longer periods in the morning. This favored blast development.

The cultivars grown in the different regions had not changed during the last few years. The reason for the 1990 blast outbreak appears to be related to weather. ■

Incidence and severity of leaf and neck blast in 1990 dry season crops in some regions of Bangladesh.

Region ^a	Area planted (x10 ³ ha)	Fields examined (no.)	Area infected (%)	Land type	Soil type	Incidence (%)		Severity (0-9)	
						LB1	NB1	LB1	NB1
I	179	28	22.8	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	10-100	5-9	3-9
II	605	35	94.1	Low medium high	Sandy loam to clay loam	3-50	1-20	3-9	2-5
III	339	25	4.5	Low medium	Clay loam	1-85	1-75	2-9	5-9
IV	215	34	19.4	Low medium	Sandy loam	2-10	1-30	1-3	1-2
V	139	27	50.0	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	5-50	4-9	1-3
All	1477	149	44.7	Low-high	Sandy loam to clay	1-100	1-100	1-9	1-9

^a I = Greater Dhaka district, II = Greater Tangail and Mymensingh districts, III = Greater Sylhet district, IV = Greater Rangpur and Dinjpur districts, V = Greater Khulna and Jessore districts. Cultivars grown: I = BR1, BR2, BR11, BR14, IR8, Pajam, and locals; II = BR1, IR8, BR14, Pajam, Purbachi, and locals; III = BR3, BR14, BR17, BR18, IR8, Pajam, and locals; IV = BR9, BR14, and locals; V = IR50, Purbachi, Ratna, and locals.

Prevailing relative humidity (RH), temperature, and number of rainy days, Jan-Mar 1989 and 1990.

Effect of plant extracts in controlling rice tungro

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We screened 32 plant species belonging to 23 families for their ability to control tungro (see list).

Extracts were prepared by grinding plant tissues with sterile water, at 1 ml water/g of tissue, in a mortar and pestle. The macerate was expressed through cotton wool and diluted by adding sterile water to 10% concentration (wt/vol). Detergent was added at 1 ml/liter of extract and the mixture sprayed on 15-d-old ADT31 rice seedlings.

Seedlings were inoculated with viruliferous green leafhoppers *Nephotettix*